

Metadata element	Content
Dataset title	AgriculturalParcel_CO2flux_Denmark_0.30_01012019_31122019
Resource abstract	Set of agricultural parcels, with their geometry, crop type, value of CO ₂ flux (due to the crop vegetation cycle during an agricultural campaign year) and a few other attributes (intermediary results, quality information).
Responsible organisation	Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark
On-line resource	Zenodo
Topic Category	environment, farming
Keyword	CO2 flux, carbon, indicator, agricultural parcels, crop type
Bounding box	Extent 598427.4413905129767954, 6088819.2711415495723486 : 710614.1919026778778061, 6200557.2807142287492752
Spatial resolution	1: 5000
Spatial representation type	vector
Coordinate reference system	EPSG:32632 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 32N
Temporal coverage	start date: 01/01/2019 end date: 31/12/2019
Conditions for access and use	Licence CCO
Limitations on public access	None
Distribution format	shapefile files (compressed as ZIP)
Resource Language	eng
Lineage	Source IACS data: - Danish LPIS - Temporal series of NDVI: Sentinel 2 images used from 01/01/2019 to 31/12/2019 Threshold - Default value (0.30) has been used